

Kinetics and mechanism of micellar catalyzed autoxidation of ethanol, propanol and *n*-butanol by *N*-bromobenzamide

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A micellar catalyzed oxidation of ethanol, propanol and *n*-butanol by *N*-bromobenzamide (NBB) in acidic medium has been studied using sodium dodecyl sulfate. The cause of autocatalysis has been attributed to Br⁻ ions, which was further substantiated by the removal of first stage on initial addition of potassium bromide. The pre-micellar catalysis by sodium dodecyl sulfate has been rationalized in the light of positive cooperativity model. The positive cooperativity indices for all the three substrates and thermodynamic parameters have been computed. The variation of solvent composition and addition of benzamide have also been studied. Most plausible mechanisms have been envisaged.

A considerable amount of work has been done by various workers on autocatalytic oxidation of primary alcohols by *N*-halo compounds in general and *N*-bromobenzamide (NBB) in particular¹ but no information is available on the autocatalyzed oxidation of primary alcohols by *N*-bromobenzamide in micellar system. Therefore, the present study of autocatalyzed oxidation of ethanol, propanol and *n*-butanol by NBB in presence of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was undertaken.

Results and discussion

Reaction rates for micellar catalyzed oxidation of ethanol, propanol and *n*-butanol depend on both alcohol and surfactant concentrations. The plots of log (*a*-*x*) versus time exhibit two linear stages. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Dependence of rate on [Alcohols] : The linear plots of

Table 1. Effect of variation of substrate concentrations

[NBB] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, [SDS] = 8.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, AcOH = 10% (v/v), temp. = 308 K

[Substrate] mol dm ⁻³	[EtOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		[PrOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		[BuOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	
	<i>k</i> ₁	<i>k</i> ' ₁	<i>k</i> ₁	<i>k</i> ' ₁	<i>k</i> ₁	<i>k</i> ' ₁
0.2	0.64	1.15	1.15	3.30	1.21	4.11
0.3	0.92	3.25	1.50	5.40	1.70	5.94
0.4	1.17	4.25	2.01	6.64	2.24	7.36
0.5	1.52	5.12	2.66	7.71	2.98	9.54
0.6	1.78	6.23	3.34	9.65	3.34	11.0
0.8	2.41	7.55	4.66	10.7	4.42	16.4

Table 2. Effect of surfactant concentration

[NBB] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [substrate] = 0.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, AcOH = 10% (v/v), temp. = 308 K

[SDS] mol dm ⁻³	[EtOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		[PrOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		[BuOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	
	<i>k</i> ₁	<i>k</i> ' ₁	<i>k</i> ₁	<i>k</i> ' ₁	<i>k</i> ₁	<i>k</i> ' ₁
0.0	0.59	3.37	0.92	5.88	0.98	6.39
2.0	0.98	3.89	1.38	6.92	1.56	8.28
4.0	1.33	4.90	2.25	7.80	2.45	10.62
6.0	1.93	6.22	3.33	9.04	3.67	12.23
8.0	2.41	7.55	4.66	10.07	4.82	15.32
10.0	3.01	8.91	5.08	11.82	6.12	16.32
13.0	3.76	9.04	6.23	12.04	6.88	17.45
15.0	3.80	9.24	6.38	12.13	7.02	17.62
17.0	3.85	9.31	6.45	12.27	7.33	17.75

log *k*₁ (log *k*'₁) vs log [substrate] give slope values equal to 0.97 (*r*² = 0.99) and 1.17 (*r*² = 0.92) for ethanol, 1.03 (*r*² = 0.98) and 1.01 (*r*² = 0.98) for propanol and 1.04 (*r*² = 0.99) and 0.97 (*r*² = 0.994) for *n*-butanol, respectively, for the first and second stages (Table 1). Thus the order of reaction with respect to each substrate is one.

Dependence of rate on [SDS] : Reactions have been found to be catalyzed (Table 2) by the addition of SDS, an anionic surfactant². The pre-micellar catalysis (2.0 × 10⁻³ to 20.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) is probably due to the fact that small aggregates of the surfactant molecules exit below the cmc and that they start catalyzing the reaction³. The Piszkiwicz model⁴ for pre-micellar catalysis is given by eqn. (1),

$$\log [k_{\text{obs}} - k_0/k_m - k_{\text{obs}}] = n \log [D] - \log K_D \quad (1)$$

In the present case, the plots of $\log [k_{\text{obs}} - k_0/k_m - k_{\text{obs}}]$ vs $\log [D]$ are linear with slope values for ethanol, propanol and *n*-butanol to be 1.47, 1.72 and 1.83, respectively, indicating a positive cooperativity, i.e. induced interaction of the additional substrate molecule due to the interaction of the micelle with the first substrate molecule.

Effect of variation of sulfuric acid: Lower slopes value (less than one) suggests that H^+ plays complex role in the reaction mechanism.

Temperature and solvent effects: All the kinetic and activation parameters have been calculated (Table 3). Large

Table 3. Kinetic and activation parameters

[NBB] = 2.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [substrate] = 0.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [SDS] = 8.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, AcOH = 10% (v/v)

Substrate	ΔE^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔPZ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	ΔS^* J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
EtOH	I stage	70.5	1.29×10^7	-89.9	95.6
	II stage	52.5	2.98×10^5	-140.4	93.2
PrOH	I stage	61.3	4.76×10^6	-117.4	94.9
	II stage	59.6	9.94×10^6	-111.3	91.3
BuOH	I stage	63.6	1.36×10^7	-108.6	94.5
	II stage	60.0	1.25×10^7	-109.5	91.2

negative values of ΔS^* can be explained on the basis of the involvement of bulkier species, hypobromite formation. The normal frequency factor values suggest the involvement of a neutral molecule in the rate-determining step. The almost constant values of ΔE^* suggest similar reaction mechanisms for all the substrates. The reactions are remarkably affected by the variation in solvent composition (Table 4). Amis⁵ plots for all the three substrates, i.e. plots of $\log k_1$ ($\log k'_1$)

Table 4. Variation of solvent composition

[NBB] = 2.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [substrate] = 0.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [SDS] = 8.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, AcOH = 10% (v/v), [H₂SO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³

AcOH %	D	[EtOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		[PrOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		[BuOH] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	
		k_1	k'_1	k_1	k'_1	k_1	k'_1
10	67.00	1.46	3.74	1.92	7.71	2.24	6.39
20	60.25	1.55	4.04	2.31	8.41	2.43	8.93
30	53.50	1.72	4.54	2.45	9.19	2.83	10.03
40	47.00	1.87	5.13	2.96	10.32	3.36	11.47
50	39.80	2.37	6.31	3.96	12.43	4.30	14.43

vs $1/D$, are linear with positive slopes. The increase in the rate constant with the decrease in dielectric constant suggests the involvement of a neutral molecule in the rate-determining step.⁶

Effect of addition of Br⁻ and benzamide: Addition of bromide ions results in the removal of slow step. The reaction becomes simple single step in all the three cases with the magnitude of rate constants found almost the same as that of the corresponding second stages⁷. The reaction rate has been found to be retarded with the incremental addition of benzamide, and this confirms the formation of benzamide in the pre-equilibrium stage.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of the reaction is

The product analysis was done under the kinetic conditions. A mixture of alcohol (0.05 mol), SDS (0.005 mol) and NBB (0.01 mol) was made upto 50 ml in H₂SO₄ and kept in dark for 24 h until the completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated overnight with excess (200 ml) saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNP) in 2 mol dm⁻³ hydrochloric acid. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was collected by filtration and its identity was confirmed by the determination of melting point and TLC with standard.

Mechanism: The following reaction mechanisms have been envisioned for the first and subsequently second stage. *N*-Bromobenzamide like similar *N*-haloamides may exist in various forms in the acid medium, viz. free NBB, protonated NBB, Br⁺, molecular bromine and HOBr/H₂O⁺Br. The different forms of reactive species for oxidant can be represented by the following equilibria.

If free NBB were the active species in the rate-determining step, addition of benzamide would have increased the reaction rate. However, addition of benzamide in the reaction system decreases the reaction rate. This can be easily explained in the light of the eqm. (1) where benzamide and HOBr are produced. Addition of benzamide shifts the equilibrium to the left thereby reducing the concentration of HOBr/H₂O⁺Br, which is the main oxidizing species, resulting in the retardation of the reaction rates.

Micellar catalyzed mechanism for first stage : In micellar catalyzed reaction, the first step envisioned is the formation of micelle due to aggregation of detergent molecules followed by micelle-substrate interaction to form (SDS)_n....RCH₂OH. It is followed by the slow step of oxidation by H₂O⁺Br. In the subsequent fast step final products are obtained :

Mechanism for second stage : It was observed that after about 20% completion of the reaction the solution becomes yellowish. This is obviously due to the liberation of bromine. It is formed due to the interaction between the unreacted NBB and bromide ion, one of the products of the reaction. Bromide ions come into the system as a result of eqn. (5). The removal of first stage on addition of potassium bromide supports this. The production of bromine by an autocatalytic reaction was further confirmed by the addition of mercury(II), a bromocomplexing agent, as it forms unionized mercury-bromo-complexes and removes the first stage⁹. Bromine formed as a result of eqm. (6) will simultaneously start oxidizing the micelle-substrate moiety as :

The above mechanism leads to the following rate expression for the first stage : $-d[\text{NBB}]/dt = k_1 [n \text{ SDS}] [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHBr}][\text{RCH}_2\text{OH}]/[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONH}_2]$

$$\text{where, } k_1 = \frac{k_w K_m K_D K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHBr}]}{(K_{-1} + K_1 [\text{H}^+])[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONH}_2]}$$

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of ethanol and propanol were prepared in distilled water while that of *n*-butanol was prepared in glacial acetic acid. Acetic acid was distilled over chromic acid before use. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric estimations of the reaction mixture at various time intervals. To avoid photochemical effect the reaction bottle was painted black.

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References

1. V. Vyas, K. Kothari, S. Banerji and K. Banerji, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 112. K. Choudhary, S. Banerji and K. K. Banerji, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 5391. B. T. Gowda, T. Rao and P. J. Mohna, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 148; O. N. Choubé and S. K. Awasthi, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 1998, **14**, 347; V. K. Seriah and N. M. Gupta, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2000, **12**, 1071.
2. P. V. S. Rao, G. K. Rao, K. Ramkrishana, G. Rambabu and A. Satyanarayan, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1997, **29**, 171.
3. C. A. Bunton, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 1997, **72**, 231, and reference cited therein; P. S. Raghavan, V. S. Shrivivasanand and N. Venkatasubramanian, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 42; P. S. Radhakrishnamurty, B. S. Sasmal and D. P. Patnaik, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 216.
4. D. Piszkievicz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 1550.
5. E. S. Amis, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rate and Mechanism", Academic, New York, 1966.
6. K. J. Laidler, "Chemical Kinetics", Tata McGraw-Hills, New Delhi, 1977.
7. N. Venkatasubramanian and V. Thiagarajan, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 694.
8. R. Bruice and E. H. Cordes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 4395.
9. S. Reddy and E. V. Sundaram, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 543.